

**CULTURAL PAREMIOLOGICAL EXPRESSIONS RELATED TO TIME
IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES RELATIONSHIPS ABOUT
THEIR IMPORTANCE IN REFLECTING CHANGE**

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Annotation: The proverb, which is considered one of the ancient examples of folklore, is different. It is different from other genres due to its short, concise, figurative and deep content stands out. The ancient and rich spirituality of each nation through proverbs appears. Proverbs are extremely rich and diverse in terms of subject matter can be used literally or figuratively. For proverbs as an object, persons, things, and at the same time, animals are taken. The proverbs are mainly didactic in nature and are written by Bahadir Sarimsakov stated that "proverbs can also be used figuratively has This feature defines the thematic scope of proverbs, the level of application expands".

Key words: folklore, proverb, negative character, image, content, figurative meaning.

This is definitely the unity of the spiritual culture created by the people are proverbs of the people. The oral or personal memory of each nation let's take a look at it, the myths that are vividly preserved in the memory of mankind, primitive ideas and concepts from the depths of long history, centuries. The cream of life wisdom derived from observations during the course is human we see the reflection of thought experience. There are also English and Uzbek folk proverbs it is a product of scientific and artistic thinking that has been collected and polished over thousands of years It is the best that has arisen as, is said among the people, refined, and passed from generation to generation. It is one of the spiritual heritages. Created and used in the past the best proverbs of the bride, as an example of folk wisdom, now is also of great educational value. Such proverbs and wise words it is a precious treasure of the spiritual wealth of every nation.

There are a lot of animal names, that is, zoonyms, in folk proverbs occurs. Zoonyms are figurative in almost all proverbs is expressed. By citing animal images, human characteristics are animals it is shown through, that is, the instructive idea given in

the proverbs is given in the proverb it is not said about animals, but about people. Mostly animals people with a negative character are criticized. Each There are proverbs that express the unique characteristics of the nation. We are this structure and semantics of Uzbek and English folk proverbs in our small study We will do a comparative analysis. There are a lot of animal names, that is, zoonyms, in folk proverbs occurs. Zoonyms are figurative in almost all proverbs is expressed. By citing animal images, human characteristics are animals it is shown through, that is, the instructive idea given in the proverbs is given in the proverb it is not said about animals, but about people. Mostly animals people with a negative character are criticized. Each there are proverbs that express the unique characteristics of the nation. We are this structure and semantics of Uzbek and English folk proverbs in our small study .We will do a comparative analysis. A deeper analysis of proverbs and their national-cultural meanings in different languages and learning through the reflection of universal values is the present time is an urgent problem of linguistics. Comparatively speaking, we can see that all languages in the world have their own characteristics and it is this phenomenon that separates different languages from each other. But this is known as language Learners of a foreign language know the difference between their mother tongue and this language adopts on the basis of dependence. These languages are united under certain categories. These categories include grammatical categories, lexical-semantic categories, includes linguistic signs similar to functional categories. So, generalizing categories ensure universality in languages. Meanwhile, proverbs are a unique linguistic unit found in every language, and they also have a commonality there is. G. L. Permiakov thinks about it as follows: circumstances the property of generalization, that is, combining the same or similar situations with different ones found in folk proverbs. This uniformity in proverbs ensures universality and in many cases they have a special logical meaning. It follows tha the proverbial world is related to world civilization, which belongs to only one nation it is absolutely wrong to say. Universality in proverbs is the main edge of paremiology is, it summarizes similar and identical situations in proverbs and even it occurs in unrelated languages, regardless of their history and ethnicity.

So there is a lot about the possession of universal and national characteristics of proverbs studies have been conducted. Universal features in the structure of proverbs, one

if it is manifested in its spirituality and multi-spirituality and its themes, it is

the reason is historical development, increasing international relations and universality growth of values. National characteristics - national character, national spirit on the contrary, they are characteristics of a certain ethnic group. Of a certain ethnicity without knowing the necessary aspects such as place of residence, history and nationality it is absolutely impossible to understand the essence and meaning of proverbs. Proverbs to be alert, to distinguish a friend from an enemy, to be humane, to be kind, sweet words, loyal, parents, relatives and friends to appreciate, to respect the elders, to be kind to the little ones teaches: "If you walk with good, you will be good, if you walk with bad, you will stay shame", "If you respect, you will be respected". Proverbs that call people to cleanliness and health are short and simple words, but is deep, deeply meaningful and aimed at the same goal: "If your eyes hurt, put your hand stop, if your stomach hurts, stop your lust!", "A person is tougher than steel, more delicate than a flower", "Health If you wish, don't say too much, if you wish for honor, don't say too much!", "Your purity is your health". It is widespread in our nation and is one of our best spiritual heritages. That's it while inculcating the idea of national independence in the minds of young people, making them a perfect generation included wise thoughts so that it would be easy for students to understand it is appropriate to decorate our conversations with proverbs and use them effectively.

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